

MICROSTRUCTURE OF $\text{LaB}_6\text{-ZrB}_2$ IN SITU COMPOSITE PREPARED BY ELECTRON BEAM HEATED MELTING METHODS

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SUMMARY: Directional solidification of $\text{LaB}_6\text{-ZrB}_2$, by use of an electron beam heating technique, yielded orientated ZrB_2 fibers in a LaB_6 matrix. The average diameter of the ZrB_2 fibers was about 0.2-1.2 μm , with fiber lengths up to 100 μm . Primary plate-like LaB_6 dendrites formed upon the solidification of an ingot with a composition of $\text{LaB}_6\text{-18 wt\% ZrB}_2$. LaB_6 was the first phase to nucleate when eutectic growth occurred, and ZrB_2 showed a non-faceted growth. For the ingot solidified with planar growth the orientation relation of the phases was:

Growth direction : $[001]_{\text{LaB}_6} // [00.1]_{\text{ZrB}_2}$
Interfacial plane: $(\bar{1}10)_{\text{LaB}_6} // (01.0)_{\text{ZrB}_2}$

KEYWORDS: lanthanum hexaboride, zirconium diboride, eutectic microstructure, in situ composite, electron beam

INTRODUCTION

In situ composites prepared by directional solidification have received considerable attention because of their enhanced interphase bonding and microstructure stability. In the past decades, a great effort has been directed towards developing oxide-oxide [1] and metal-metal [2] eutectic in situ composites, and a few types of carbide-diboride eutectic systems [3] have also been studied. However, little work has been done on boride-boride eutectics which usually possess higher melting points. Recently, the d- and f- transition metal-boride eutectics have been studied by Paderno [4] and revealed unusual thermionic and mechanical properties. The $\text{LaB}_6\text{-ZrB}_2$ system was reported to have the best fracture toughness (up to 20.3 - 27.8 $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$) and the highest bend strength (up to 1200 MPa). It appears that the boride in situ composites are potentially a new type of structural materials with unusual mechanical properties. Although good mechanical properties of these composites have been reported, the morphology and crystallography of the $\text{LaB}_6\text{-ZrB}_2$ eutectic are not clear. The aim of this work was to investigate the microstructure and crystallography of directionally solidified $\text{LaB}_6\text{-ZrB}_2$ eutectic by using a floating zone melting furnace with electron beam heating.

EXPERIMENT

The LaB_6 and ZrB_2 powders used in the experiment were produced in Institute of Materials Problem in Ukraine. The purity of LaB_6 was >99.4%, with major impurities of 0.3% Fe and 0.1% O, and with Si and Mg as minor impurities. The purity of ZrB_2 was >98.2%, with major impurities of 0.3% Fe, 0.3% Mg and 0.15% O, and minor impurities of 0.03% Ca and 0.04% Al. The impurity concentrations were reported by the supplier.

Ordan'yan [5] reported an eutectic composition of 80 wt % LaB_6 and 20 wt % ZrB_2 , with a liquidus temperature of 2470°C, and Paderno [4] reported 79 wt % LaB_6 and 21 wt % ZrB_2 at the same temperature. As the constituents evaporate in high vacuum at high temperatures, the variation of composition may cause an irregular structure, so samples with different starting compositions were prepared to obtain the regular structure. Our experiments showed that the sample with a composition of 80 wt % LaB_6 and 20 wt % ZrB_2 had no primary phase, and this composition was preferred for our studies.

The weighed powders were blended in an ethanol slurry for 1 hr, then dry pressed and melted by electric arc to form rods. The rods are about 6 mm in diameter and 120 mm in length. Directional solidification was accomplished by a floating zone melting furnace with electron beam heating, with 10 kW of power and a vacuum of 5×10^{-5} Torr.

The final specimens were cut by electric discharging along and across the axes of the rods to get longitudinal and transverse sections. After polished with diamond paste and etched with nitric acid, the specimens were examined by ARMA Model 1000B scanning electron microscope (SEM). Line-intercept method was used to measure the interfiber spacing. Thin foils were prepared by ion beam thinning and examined by JEM-200CX transmission electron microscope (TEM) to determine the crystallography of the eutectic phases.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All the samples by zone melting had a gray surface layer, probably because of higher evaporation rate of LaB_6 than ZrB_2 at high temperature, as higher concentration of LaB_6 was determined in the substance collected from the furnace inwall than that in the ingot and almost single ZrB_2 phase was formed on the surface of the samples. The slower the growth rate, the thicker the surface layer formed on the sample, and cracks usually occurred on the layer, probably because of evaporation of boride at a solid state. Fig. 1 shows the scanning electron

Fig. 1. Scanning electron micrographs of ingots with eutectic composition. (A) Longitudinal section and (B) transverse section.

micrographs of an ingot at eutectic composition solidified at a rate of 2.5 mm/min. The structure consists of very fine orientated ZrB_2 fibers (light phase) uniformly distributed in the matrix of lanthanum hexaboride. The average diameter of ZrB_2 fibers was about 0.2-1.2 μm , with fiber lengths up to 100 μm . The fibers were generally parallel to the rod axis, as the growth direction follows the thermal gradient. Considerable off-axis growth was observed at the periphery of rods, especially at higher growth rates. Disrupted structure was observed in the eutectic samples, as shown in Fig. 2(A). The disrupted structure was seen in the early stage of growth in metal eutectics [6] before establishment of a preferred orientation, so the growth direction may not be the preferred orientation in LaB_6 - ZrB_2 system when observing the disrupted structure. Another reason for the formation of the disrupted structure may be a power fluctuation. As boride evaporated and trapped gas run out when the primary rod began melting, the electron beam emission may be blocked because of bad vacuum and the power may fluctuate abruptly. This may cause nucleation in front of the liquid/solid interface before a preferred growth occurred along the thermal gradient. In this case, the nucleated phase appears to be LaB_6 , and ZrB_2 fiber branching was observed in the eutectic grain formed afterwards.

In certain growth condition, the non-planar front was obtained. Fig. 2(B) is an example of longitudinal section showing a cellular growth, and "colony" structure was formed at a growth rate of 8 mm/min. As growth direction is normal to the solid-liquid interface, the planar interface must be maintained to obtain well orientated eutectic structure.

Fig. 2. SEM micrography of eutectic ingot along the longitudinal section showing (A) disrupted structure and (B) colony structure.

The rods with off-eutectic compositions were also directionally solidified at a growth rate of 1.5 mm/min. Fig. 3 shows a SEM micrograph of a sample with a hypoeutectic composition of

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of hypoeutectic ingots. (A) Longitudinal section and (B) transverse section

The rods with off-eutectic compositions were also directionally solidified at a growth rate of 1.5 mm/min. Fig. 3 shows a SEM micrograph of a sample with a hypoeutectic composition of

$\text{LaB}_6\text{-ZrB}_2$. Primary plate-like LaB_6 appears, and obviously different width of LaB_6 plates is observed along the growth direction. In a transverse section of the sample, some rectangular LaB_6 phase are observed and the spiral growth appears parallel to $[001]_{\text{LaB}_6}$ direction. Such orientation assumption would agree with tetragonal symmetry of lanthanum hexaboride and the observed circular growth morphology of spirals. The similar behavior has been observed where growth morphology and crystallographic orientations are very closely coupled [7,8]. The eutectic appears to grow directly from the primary lanthanum hexaboride. In Fig. 4, a transverse section of a hypereutectic ingot, primary ZrB_2 clearly grows in a dendritic manner and has a layer of LaB_6 surrounding it before any eutectic appears.

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of hypereutectic ingots along the transverse section showing the morphology of primary ZrB_2 phase.

Fig. 5 shows a transmission electron micrograph and an electron diffraction pattern taken from a longitudinal section of an eutectic ingot at a growth rate of 2.5 mm/min. The fibers were well orientated along the growth direction and the interfacial plains were smooth. This suggests that low energy interface be formed in this system. The growth direction of the LaB_6 matrix and the ZrB_2 fibers were $[001]_{\text{LaB}_6}$ and $[00.1]_{\text{ZrB}_2}$ direction respectively, which were perpendicular to $(001)_{\text{LaB}_6}$ plane. The crystallographic relation between the matrix and the fiber deduced from Fig. 5(B) was:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Growth direction : } & [001]_{\text{LaB}_6} // [00.1]_{\text{ZrB}_2} \\ \text{Interfacial plane : } & (\bar{1}10)_{\text{LaB}_6} // (01.0)_{\text{ZrB}_2} \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 5. (A) Transmission electron micrograph and (B) selected area electron diffraction for the longitudinal direction of $\text{LaB}_6\text{-ZrB}_2$ eutectic.

Fig. 6 shows the structural relation between LaB_6 and ZrB_2 phases. It is known that lanthanum hexaboride has a cubic CaB_6 -type structure with a single cubic arrangement of metal atoms centered by boron atom octahedron. The zirconium diboride has hexagonal AlB_2 type structure with alternate crystallographic plane along the hexagonal c axis, having flat hexagonal nets of metal or boron atoms. The intraoctahedral B-B distance in lanthanum hexaboride and B-B distance in zirconium diboride in the flat hexagonal net are 0.1765 nm and 0.1829 nm respectively. The lattice mismatch between the matrix and the fiber is only 3.16%, well below the critical value of 16% for a semicoherent interface[1].

Fig. 6. Structural relation between LaB_6 and ZrB_2 phases during cocrystallization. B-B' is a common boron pair shared by both phases.

CONCLUSIONS

Orientated microstructures of $\text{LaB}_6\text{-ZrB}_2$ system have been produced by use of a electron beam heated floating zone melting method. For the ingots with planar growth, both phases grow in the [001] directions with orientation: $(\bar{1}10)_{\text{LaB}_6} // (01.0)_{\text{ZrB}_2}$. The misfit between the two phases was calculated to be below the critical value of 16% for a semicoherent interface.

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